

What variables (proxies) which provide information on soil systems do we not record, but which are important for an integrated approach to sustainable land management?

What one thing would most improve your ability to work with soil data from agricultural areas, within a sustainability framework?

Theme: Improving soil data in agricultural areas to enable environmentally sustainable land management practices

What data on soils which is widely used in your domain is underused and relevant for another domain?

What data on soils used in your domain is hardest to interpret reliably and with appropriate nuance?

Theme: Breaking down data, methods and knowledge silos between agricultural, environmental, cultural and natural heritage domains



For continuous monitoring data on different soil properties, what is the cadence of updates needed to inform sustainable management?

What proxies are used in different domains?

Focus on proxy data provided by sensors. How do they need to be deployed?

Theme: Assessing data requirements and diversifying data sources for agri-environmental monitoring and management, and overlaps with cultural and natural heritage monitoring and management requirements

What approach would you recommend to address problems of data patchiness: acquiring more spatially detailed and temporally consistent data, assembling a more diverse set of complementary data, or improving modelling approaches to work with irregular data?

How important is it to have consistent data regionally or nationally?

To what extent can data be site-specific or acquisitions be opportunistic?

Theme: Addressing problems introduced by data patchiness (irregular coverage spatially and temporally) and biases in distributions, which prevent scaling up of predictions and models

In your domain of expertise, how do you decide where to sample, sense, or take a measurement, and what criteria inform that plan?

In your domain, what national or other standard practice do you apply to your sampling regime or data?

In your domain, what kind of barriers limit your ability to acquire the representative, timely and accurate data you need, or your ability to apply a standard?

Theme: Good practice for sensor and data acquisition and management protocols for natural environment scaled deployments

